

Proof of Conjecture based on Erdős–Moser Equation

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Abstract

There is no more solution than $1+2=3$ in Erdős–Moser equation.

1 Introduction

Erdős–Moser problem is as following[Gallot et al.(2011)Gallot, Moree, and Zudilin]:

Does the Erdős–Moser equation have solutions other than $1^1 + 2^1 = 3^1$?

With Erdős–Moser equation being stated as following:

$$1^k + 2^k + 3^k + 4^k + \dots + (m-1)^k = m^k \quad (m, k \in \mathbb{N})$$

2 Dividing Cases

Suppose that there is m, k that fits the equation other than $m = 3, k = 1$.

$$\begin{aligned} 1^k + 2^k + 3^k + 4^k + \dots + (m-1)^k &= m^k \quad (m, k \in \mathbb{N}) \\ \Rightarrow \text{Odd}^k + \text{Even}^k + \text{Odd}^k + \text{Even}^k + \dots &= (\text{Odd or Even})^k \end{aligned}$$

For dividing cases for upper occasion:

$$\begin{cases} \text{Case 1. } \text{Odd}^k + \text{Even}^k + \text{Odd}^k + \text{Even}^k + \dots + \text{Odd}^k = (\text{Odd or Even})^k \text{ under s.t. } \text{Even}^k \\ \text{Case 2. } \text{Odd}^k + \text{Even}^k + \text{Odd}^k + \text{Even}^k + \dots + \text{Even}^k = (\text{Odd or Even})^k \text{ under s.t. } \text{Odd}^k \end{cases}$$

2.1 Case 1

For case 1 to fit equation, m^k must be even.

$$\begin{cases} \text{Case 1-1. } (4 \cdot 1 - 3)^k + (4 \cdot 1 - 2)^k + (4 \cdot 1 - 1)^k + (4 \cdot 1)^k + \dots + (4 \cdot x - 3)^k = (4x - 2)^k \\ \text{Case 1-2. } (4 \cdot 1 - 3)^k + (4 \cdot 1 - 2)^k + (4 \cdot 1 - 1)^k + (4 \cdot 1)^k + \dots + (4 \cdot x - 1)^k = (4x)^k \end{cases}$$

In these cases, case 1-1 is falsified under circumstance that number of odd is not even. Then case 1-2 leaves only.

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2.2 Case 2

For case 2 to fit equation, m^k must be odd.

$$\begin{cases} \text{Case 2-1. } (4 \cdot 1 - 3)^k + (4 \cdot 1 - 2)^k + (4 \cdot 1 - 1)^k + (4 \cdot 1)^k + \dots + (4 \cdot x - 2)^k = (4x - 1)^k \\ \text{Case 2-2. } (4 \cdot 1 - 3)^k + (4 \cdot 1 - 2)^k + (4 \cdot 1 - 1)^k + (4 \cdot 1)^k + \dots + (4 \cdot x)^k = (4x + 1)^k \end{cases}$$

In these cases, case 2-2 is falsified under circumstance that number of odd is not odd. Then case 2-1 leaves only.

3 Generalization

$$\begin{cases} \text{Case 1-2. } (4 \cdot 1 - 3)^k + (4 \cdot 1 - 2)^k + (4 \cdot 1 - 1)^k + (4 \cdot 1)^k + \dots + (4 \cdot x - 1)^k = (4x)^k \\ \text{Case 2-1. } (4 \cdot 1 - 3)^k + (4 \cdot 1 - 2)^k + (4 \cdot 1 - 1)^k + (4 \cdot 1)^k + \dots + (4 \cdot x - 2)^k = (4x - 1)^k \end{cases}$$

With extending case 1-2 and 2-1, multiplier can be doubled.

$$\begin{cases} \text{Case 1-2-1. } (8 \cdot 1 - 7)^k + (8 \cdot 1 - 6)^k + (8 \cdot 1 - 5)^k + (8 \cdot 1 - 4)^k + \dots + (8 \cdot x - 5)^k = (8x - 4)^k \\ \text{Case 1-2-2. } (8 \cdot 1 - 7)^k + (8 \cdot 1 - 6)^k + (8 \cdot 1 - 5)^k + (8 \cdot 1 - 4)^k + \dots + (8 \cdot x - 1)^k = (8x)^k \\ \text{Case 2-1-1. } (8 \cdot 1 - 7)^k + (8 \cdot 1 - 6)^k + (8 \cdot 1 - 5)^k + (8 \cdot 1 - 4)^k + \dots + (8 \cdot x - 6)^k = (8x - 5)^k \\ \text{Case 2-1-2. } (8 \cdot 1 - 7)^k + (8 \cdot 1 - 6)^k + (8 \cdot 1 - 5)^k + (8 \cdot 1 - 4)^k + \dots + (8 \cdot x - 2)^k = (8x - 1)^k \end{cases}$$

Again, case 1-2-1 and case 2-1-2 is falsified. This can be generalized with $o, x, n \in \mathbb{Z}$ given:

$$\begin{cases} \text{Case A. } \sum_a^{2^x \cdot o} a^k + (2^x \cdot o + 1)^k + \dots + (2^x \cdot o + 2^x - 1)^k = (2^x \cdot o + 2^x)^k \\ \text{Case B. } \sum_a^{2^x \cdot o} a^k + (2^x \cdot o + 1)^k + (2^x \cdot o + 2)^k = (2^x o + 3)^k \end{cases}$$

Case A is falsified with disparity between odd and even. This leaves case B only. As more generalization with taken $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ as given :

$$\dots + n^k + (n + 1)^k + (n + 2)^k = (n + 3)^k$$

Upper case fits the statement of the problem only. The case of $n = 0$ is the only case fits the condition. So, conjecture based on Erdős–Moser stated in introduction turns out to be there is no more solution than $1^1 + 2^1 = 3^1$.

References

- [Gallot et al.(2011)Gallot, Moree, and Zudilin] Yves Gallot, Pieter Moree, and Wadim Zudilin. The erdős–moser equation $1^k + 2^k + \dots + (m - 1)^k = m^k$ revisited using continued fractions. *Mathematics of Computation*, 80(274):1221–1221, May 2011. ISSN 0025-5718. doi: 10.1090/s0025-5718-2010-02439-1. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1090/S0025-5718-2010-02439-1>.